

Experimental analysis of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with EBR-CFRP sheets under indoor and outdoor environment

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The present work is based on the experimental analysis of reinforced concrete beams strengthened CFRP sheets applied according to the EBR technique when maintained in a laboratory environment or exposed to weathering. In addition, the intervening materials were also exposed to the same environmental conditions as the beams. The results indicate that the weather-exposed epoxy adhesives presented reductions in mechanical properties, while the CFRP composite properties remained similar after exposure. The tests conducted after 6 and 27 months showed a 6.4 and 10.1% reduction in the load-carrying capacity of the strengthened beams kept in a laboratory environment or exposed to weathering, respectively.

KEYWORDS

Reinforced concrete beams; Strengthening; CFRP sheets; Degradation; EBR technique.

This paper reports the continuation of a long-term study of FRP durability. Early results from this study (14 days and six months of data) were reported previously by Dalfré *et al.* (2021). The present paper reports continued data for 27 months and, in the interest of clarity and continuity, repeats much of the data from the previous study. Much of the project, specimen and test descriptions are also repeated. The CICE 2023 editors have approved the inclusion of this note.

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INTRODUCTION

All materials used in the construction industry are subject to degradation, originated from chemical, physical, or mechanical sources. Thus, these degradation mechanisms should be considered to achieve better long-term behaviour and durability when applying an FRP strengthening system to a reinforced concrete element (Isis, 2006). Degradation mechanisms can occur either individually or together in the degradation of the composite FRP material, as presented in Figure 1.

Figure 1: Degradation mechanisms of FRP systems (Isis, 2006)

It is known that degradation mechanisms directly affect the most sensitive part of the strengthened structure, i.e., the bond between the concrete substrate and the FRP composite, which is susceptible to degradation in harsh environments. It is found in the literature that the polymeric matrix (resins/epoxy adhesives) are susceptible to ultraviolet (UV) radiation, temperature, humidity, and acid rain (Shokrieh and Bayat, 2007). Unless a protective layer is used, the FRP gets directly exposed to the external environment and, consequently, to possible aggressive agents or eventualities. Direct exposure of the

polymeric matrix to UV radiation can result in photodegradation, which causes the decomposition or dissociation of chemical bonds between polymer chains, driven by the UV radiation in solar waves. This radiation causes the degradation of polymers, leading to discolouration, surface oxidation, embrittlement, and polymer matrix microcracking (Isis, 2006).

The intensity of weathering effects depends on the climate and microclimate where the structure is allocated. One way to categorize the climate is through the Köppen–Geiger climate classification system, which is used worldwide in different areas and considers the average annual and monthly temperature and precipitation values in addition to climate seasonality.

According to the Brazilian Agricultural Research Company (EMBRAPA, 2019), the city of São Carlos in the state of São Paulo (latitude 21°57'42" (S), longitude 47°50'28" (W), and altitude 860 meters above sea level), which is where this research was developed, has a local climate defined as humid subtropical with dry winter and hot summer (known as C_{wa}). Considering other regions of the world with similar C_{wa} climate types, as per the Köppen–Geiger climate classification system, the results and analysis obtained in this research can also be expanded worldwide. More details can be found in Ferreira (2019). So, little is known about the behaviour and durability of the strengthening systems applied on concrete substrata and the possible loss of performance due to the degradation of the intervening materials due to the natural ageing process of the structures and also due to the exposure of the externally strengthened elements to aggressive environments. In this context, the present work is based on the experimental analysis of the behaviour of reinforced concrete beams strengthened with Carbon Fiber Reinforced Polymer (CFRP), applied according to the Externally Bonded Reinforcement (EBR) technique, maintained in a laboratory environment (indoor and protected) or exposed to weathering (outdoor exposure) in a humid subtropical climate with dry winter and hot summer (C_{wa}) in non-accelerated tests performed after 6 and 27 months.

EXPERIMENTAL PROGRAM

Beam geometry, degradation environments, strengthening system and bending test configuration

The experimental program consisted of twelve simply supported beams of 120 x 200 x 2500 mm³, 20 MPa, and positive longitudinal reinforcement composed of two CA-50 steel bars (10 mm diameter; reinforcement ratio of 0.75%). To avoid shear rupture, CA-60 steel stirrups (5 mm diameter and 10 cm spacing) with two top longitudinal reinforcement bars of CA-50 and 6.3 mm diameter (Figure 2). The beams were designed in the deformation domain 2, based on the design performed by using NBR 6118 (ABNT, 2014).

Figure 2: RC concrete beams (Dalfre *et al.*, 2021. Units in mm).

EBR strengthening technique

Two of the twelve beams had no strengthening, and the others were strengthened in flexure with one layer of unidirectional CFRP sheet with 300 g/m² weight and 0.13 mm thickness, applied according to the EBR technique (Figure 3). The sheets were cut into 110 x 2200 mm strips and bonded to the tension surface of the elements, externally applied to the beams when they were 186 days old. The steps and procedures used to strengthen the reinforced concrete beams can be found in Ferreira (2019) and Dalfre *et al.* (2021).

Figure 3: Details of the strengthening system (units in mm)

Degradation environments

Two exposure environments were adopted in this research, as given below.

- Laboratory environment (LAB): internal to a chamber, protected, and with monitoring of ambient temperature and humidity, which served as a reference for the other tests (Figure 4a); and
- Exposure to weathering (WEA): external environment, free of obstacles that promoted shading in beams and specimens, and with monitoring of humidity, temperature, and radiation (Figure 4b).

Figure 4: Exposure environments (Dalfre *et al.*, 2021): (a) isolated and protected chamber (Laboratory) and (b) exposure to weather (outdoor environment)

Each beam was identified as $V_{x_y_w_z}$, where "x" is the number of tested elements, "y" corresponds to the elements used as reference (REF, of *Reference*), maintained in a laboratory environment (LAB, of *laboratory*), or exposed to weathering (WEA, of *Weathering*), "w" due to the use or not of strengthening material (0 or 1 layer of CFRP sheet), and "z" corresponds to the age when the test was carried out (14 days, 6 months or 27 months after applying the strengthening system). Table 1 presents a summary of the experimental program wherein $V_{x_REF_0_14d}$ and $V_{x_REF_CFRP_14d}$ refer to the beams without and with strengthening, respectively, maintained in the same environment and tested on the same date – 14 days after applying the CFRP sheets – which were considered as references for the

other analyses. The V_x_LAB_CFRP_6m and V_x_WEA_CFRP_6m refer to the beams strengthened with CFRP, maintained in a laboratory chamber environment, or exposed to weathering, and tested 6 months after the strengthening application.

Test configuration

The three points bending tests were performed with midspan point load, using a universal EMIC testing machine (model DL 60000 available at the Structural Systems Laboratory (LSE) of the Federal University of São Carlos (UFSCar). Figure 5 shows the instrumentation used.

Table 1: Test program for the RC beams

	Group identification	Environment	Beams ID	Condition for performing the test	Number of tested beams
Reference	V_REF_0 (No strengthening)	LAB	V1_REF_0_14d V2_REF_0_14d	Test conducted at the age of 200 days	2
	V_REF_CFRP	LAB	V1_REF_CFRP_14d V2_REF_CFRP_14d	Strengthening applied at the age of 186 days. Test performed at the age of 200 days (14 days after application of the strengthening system)	2
6 months	V_LAB_CFRP-6m	LAB	V1_LAB_CFRP_6m V2_LAB_CFRP_6m	Strengthening applied at the age of 186 days. Test performed 380 days after casting (6 months after the application of the strengthening system)	2
	V_WEA_CFRP-6m	WEA	V1_WEA_CFRP_6m V2_WEA_CFRP_6m		2
27 months	V_LAB_CFRP-27m	LAB	V1_LAB_CFRP_27m V2_LAB_CFRP_27m	Strengthening applied at the age of 186 days Test performed 1010 days after casting (27 months after the application of the strengthening system)	2
	V_WEA_CFRP-27m	WEA	V1_WEA_CFRP_27m V2_WEA_CFRP_27m		2

The loading was applied at a rate of 0.5 mm/min. The load application was double-recorded using an external 200 kN load cell (with a reading resolution of 0.01 kN), in addition to the test machine load cell, which had a load cell with a maximum capacity of 600 kN and a reading resolution of 0.1 kN. The displacements and deformations in concrete, longitudinal reinforcement, and CFRP composite were recorded using an ADS-2000 model data acquisition system (manufactured by LYNX). Beam instrumentation included a displacement transducer and six electrical strain gauges. A *Vishay* displacement transducer, with a linear range of 50 mm, was used to measure the vertical displacement of the beams, fixed to an external support, and positioned at the midspan at the beams.

The deformations in the concrete were measured on an electric strain gauge of type PA-06-1500BA-120 (resistance of 120 Ω and length of the reading grid of 40 mm, produced by Excel Sensors), which was positioned in the middle of the beams (SG1). The deformations in the longitudinal strengthening were measured on electrical strainers of type KFG-20-120-C1-11 (resistance of 120 Ω and length of the reading grid of 20 mm, produced by KYOWA), which was positioned in the mid-span of one of the longitudinal strengthening (SG2). Concerning the CFRP composite deformations, electrical strain gages of type KFG-20-120-C1-11 (the same used in longitudinal strengthening) and type PA-06-250BA-120

(resistance of 120 Ω and reading grid length of 6 mm, produced by Excel Sensors), positioned along the strengthening material (SG3 to SG5).

Characterization of materials

Characterizing the concrete included an analysis of the axial compressive strength and modulus of elasticity. Molding and curing procedures were performed, as prescribed by NBR 5738 (ABNT, 2015), and cylindrical specimens 200 mm in height and 100 mm in diameter were molded.

Figure 5: Instrumentation used in beam testing (Dalfre *et al.*, 2021. Units in mm)

Twenty-four hours after the casting, the specimens were demolded and positioned in the same environment as the beams.

The CFRP composite manufacturing system, which supplies the fiber and matrix separately, is known as the *in situ* cured system, and was used in this work.

A layer of unidirectional carbon fiber mat weighing 300 g/m² was impregnated with epoxy resin. The carbon fiber sheet had to have at least tensile strength of 3800 MPa, modulus of elasticity of 240 GPa, and deformation at rupture of 15.5%. More information on the characterization of the CFRP composites and experimental results can be found in Ferreira (2019) and Dalfre *et al.* (2021).

The adhesives used to fix the composite strengthening system to the concrete substrate were supplied by the same manufacturer of the carbon fiber sheet used in this work. In the experiment, bi-component epoxy primer and lamination resins were used. The characterization tests of epoxy resins and CFRP composites were carried out at the Polymer Laboratory of the Materials Engineering Department (DEMa) of UFSCar. More information on the characterization of adhesives and the experiment results can also be found in Ferreira (2019) and Dalfre *et al.* (2021).

The mechanical properties of the steel were evaluated by axial tensile tests, according to the recommendations of NBR 6892-1 (ABNT, 2018). At least three specimens, 50 cm in length and randomly chosen, were tested for each bar diameter used. Both steel and concrete characterization tests were performed at LSE.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

This section presents the results of the tests of characterization of the materials and the behavior of concrete beams without strengthening and strengthened with one layer of CFRP sheet and kept in the laboratory condition or exposed to weathering and tested after 14 days, 6 and 27 months.

Mechanical properties

Concrete

Concrete properties were tested 28 days after casting and on the day of the beam tests, which were performed at 200 days (REF), 380 and 1010 days (LAB and WEA). The results showed the average values of compressive strength of 22.0 MPa ($\pm 3.50\%$), 28.5 MPa ($\pm 0.54\%$) and modulus of elasticity of 29.3 GPa ($\pm 7.03\%$) and 31.6 GPa ($\pm 5.32\%$) obtained at 28 and 200 days, respectively. For the specimens that were kept in the laboratory environment (LAB), average values of 27.4 MPa ($\pm 0.50\%$) and 24.3 MPa ($\pm 1.35\%$) for compressive strength and 31.2 GPa ($\pm 2.87\%$) and 27.3 GPa ($\pm 9.17\%$) for modulus of elasticity, respectively, were obtained in the test performed at the age of 380 and 1010 days. Concerning to the specimens exposed to weathering (WEA), average values of 25.2 MPa ($\pm 6.94\%$) and 26.7 MPa ($\pm 1.96\%$) for compressive strength and 28.5 GPa ($\pm 3.06\%$) and 27.7 GPa ($\pm 3.28\%$) for modulus of elasticity, respectively, were obtained in the test performed at the age of 380 and 1010 days.

Steel

Regarding the characterization of steel, for bars with a diameter of 5 mm, type CA-60, an average yielding stress was observed at 2.0% of 646.9 ($\pm 4.04\%$) MPa and a maximum tensile stress of 670.6 ($\pm 3.62\%$) MPa. For steel with a diameter of 10 mm, a typical behavior of CA-50 steel was verified with a plastic plateau, with average yielding stress of 547.4 MPa ($\pm 2.13\%$), mean yielding strain of 2.8% ($\pm 1.59\%$), and maximum tensile stress of 591.5 MPa (± 6.25). The elasticity modulus verified for the 10 mm and 5 mm bars were 196.9 GPa ($\pm 1.58\%$) and 191.3 GPa ($\pm 7.19\%$), respectively.

Epoxy adhesives

The characterization tests for the two epoxy adhesives used in this work were experimentally performed at the ages of 7 and 14 days (full cure) and 4, 8, 12 and 24 months after the application of the strengthening system. Figure 5 presents the relationship between tensile stress and strain of epoxy adhesives maintained in a laboratory environment - LAB (a) or exposed to weathering - WEA (b).

Considering 14 days of the cure for Resin A (Figure 6a), which was maintained in a laboratory environment, the material presented a small increase in maximum tensile stress and modulus of elasticity (5.7% and 4.5%, respectively) at 4 months. After 8 months of exposure and with the results of the tests performed at 14 days as a reference, there was no significant change in the maximum average tensile stress of the primer. Therefore, there were no significant changes in the mode of rupture and stress-strain behavior throughout the exposure period in the laboratory environment.

Considering the exposure to the weather of Resin A (Figure 6b) and with the tests performed at 14 days as a reference, a reduction of 22.0% in tensile stress and 4.5% in the modulus of elasticity was noted at 4 months. At 8, 12 and 24 months of exposure, a huge reduction in average tensile stress (about 41.2, 51.4 and 62.3 %), while the modulus of elasticity showed a reduction of 9.0, 13.6 and 31.8 %, respectively. It was also verified for all the analyzed ages that the failure mode changed from ductile to fragile without a defined plasticization interval.

Resin B, which was maintained in a laboratory environment (Figure 6c) did not present major changes in its mechanical properties (reduction of only about 3.1% of tensile strength) up to 4 months of exposure. However, between 8 and 12 months, there was a considerable reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity, respectively. This reduction in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity did not influence the behavior of the stress-strain diagram, and the maximum stress level continued to be reached with close deformations. At 24 months, the tensile strength was already close to that obtained in the complete cure indicated by the manufacturer (14 days).

Figure 6: Tensile stress versus strain relationship of primer (a-b) and saturation (c-d) epoxy adhesives maintained in a laboratory environment or exposed to weathering

Resin B exposed to weather (Figure 6d) did not present significant changes in the stress-strain diagrams obtained for 7 and 14 days, with only a small increase in the maximum tension. After 4 months, there were remarkable losses in its mechanical properties, with a reduction in its average tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of 63.3% and 16.6%, respectively. After 8 months, the maximum tensile strength significant decrease. The reduction of ductility along with the aging of exposure was also observed with changes in the failure mode, which occurs abruptly and without plasticization.

In a study by Fernandes et al. (2015), epoxy resins were also kept in a laboratory environment for 2 years. As in the present study, the results also showed small reductions in their mechanical properties, specifically 5.5% and 6.9% in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity, respectively. The findings for the epoxy saturation resins (Resin B) exposed to weather were also verified in research conducted by Escobal (2016). The author evaluated the degradation of epoxy saturation resins exposed to weather (external environment with monitored temperature and humidity) for 4 months. The results showed losses of 44% in tensile strength after 4 months of exposure. Escobal (2016) also evaluated the same epoxy resins exposed to accelerated ageing cycles, contained by UV radiation, the temperature of 60°C, and water vapour at 50°C. The results showed a considerable reduction in the tensile strength of the resins (about 60%), as verified in the present work for resins A and B exposed to the weather.

CFRP composites

The CFRP composites presented a linear elastic behavior until their rupture, typical of fragile materials. The CFRP specimens kept in a laboratory environment (Figure 7a) did not present significant changes, presenting statistically equivalent tensile stress and modulus of elasticity. The same occurs for the specimens exposed to weathering (Figure 7b), that is, the CFRP did not show significant degradation after one year.

Cromwell *et al.* (2010) also found that the exposure of CFRP laminates to aggressive environments, such as constant humidity and saline solution, does not cause significant changes in their tensile strength and modulus of elasticity or ultimate deformation.

In another research by Dalfré (2016), there was no significant change in tensile strength and modulus of elasticity of CFRP composite specimens exposed to cycles of humidity and constant humidity 2 years of exposure.

Figure 7: Tensile stress versus strain relationship of CFRP composites maintained in a laboratory environment, LAB (a) or exposed to weathering, WEA (b)

Concrete beams behavior

The behavior of the reinforced concrete beams (with and without strengthening) exposed to the laboratory environment and weathering was analyzed based on ductility, increased load capacity, deformation of materials (concrete, steel, and CFRP), and rupture mode of the strengthening system. The stop criteria adopted for the reference beam tests without strengthening was established in terms of the deformation of the bending strengthening (at the time the deformation in the steel reached the average value of 11‰), while that adopted in the reinforced beams of reference and exposed in a laboratory environment and weather was established in terms of the failure of the strengthening system, followed by a sudden loss of load and detachment of the material.

Table 2 presents a summary of the average results obtained in the tests of the beam sets for the yielding of the steel reinforcement (ϵ_{sy}), for the concrete crushing ($\epsilon_{c,esm}$), and for the instant that the beams reach maximum loading (F_{max}). The indicator of the effectiveness of the bending strengthening system in terms of increased load capacity (IR) is also presented, which was obtained by analyzing the average load ($F = (F_{V1} + F_{V2}) / 2$) recorded for the beams without strengthening and strengthened (reference and exposed to the environments), respectively.

Table 2: Resume of the average experimental results

Group of beams	Yielding of the steel reinforcement (ϵ_{sy})					Concrete crushing ($\epsilon_{c,esm}$)					Maximum load recorded					
	F_{sy}	u_{sy}	ϵ_c	$\epsilon_{f,max}$	IR	$F_{c,esm}$	u_{esm}	ϵ_{sy}	$\epsilon_{f,max}$	IR	F_{max}	$u_{F,max}$	ϵ_c	ϵ_s	$\epsilon_{f,max}$	IR
	kN	mm	‰	‰	%	kN	mm	‰	‰	%	kN	mm	‰	‰	‰	%
REF_0_14d	21.8	10.3	- 1.8	----	----	25.4	15.6	5.2	----	----	27.0	25.2	- 6.1	11.0	----	---
REF_CFRP_14d	26.1	9.3	- 1.8	2.9	19.7	31.5	13.3	5.5	----	24.0	40.6	32.7	- 9.8	13.5	9.9	50.4
LAB_CFRP_6m	22.8	8.6	- 1.2	3.1	4.6	25.4	16.0	8.3	----	0.0	38.0	39.9	- 3.2	17.4	----	40.7
WEA_CFRP_6m	23.9	9.0	*	2.9	9.6	----	----	----	----	----	36.5	32.5	----	11.6	----	35.2
LAB_CFRP_27m	23.3	8.9	-1.2	2.7	6.9	35.4	21.1	8.2	7.7	39.3	39.0	28.1	-4.5	11.1	9.7	44.4
WEA_CFRP_27m	24.7	10.9	-1.3	2.4	13.3	34.7	22.2	8.7	6.6	36.6	36.7	26.8	-4.2	10.4	7.7	35.9

*Mechanically damaged strain gauge

In order to evaluate the effectiveness of the strengthening system with CFRP sheets applied according to the EBR technique, Figure 8 presents a comparison between the load and vertical displacement of the reference beams without strengthening (V1_REF_0_14d and V2_REF_0_14d) and strengthened (V1_REF_CFRP_14d and V2_REF_CFRP_14d). Upon analysis of Table 2 and Figure 8, it is possible to verify the effectiveness of the CFRP EBR strengthening system for the reinforced beams without strengthening and the increase in the load capacity of the strengthened beams.

Concerning to the beginning of the steel yield, it was verified that the strengthening provided an increase in the load capacity corresponding to the beginning of the longitudinal steel yielding and the maximum load of 19.7% and 50.4%, respectively. In addition, a reduction in the average vertical displacement of 9.7% for the strengthened reference beams, compared to the reference beams without strengthening due

to the reduction of cracking that the strengthening system promotes, restricting the reduction of element inertia, was observed.

Considering the failure modes, the reference beams without strengthening, V1_REF_0_14d and V2_REF_0_14d, designed in Domain 2, presented a ductile rupture characterized by the yielding of the longitudinal tensile reinforcement and later crushing of the compressed concrete. All the strengthened beams (V1_y_CFRP and V2_y_CFRP), after great deformation and high curvature of the elements, showed appearances of cracks parallel to the strengthening material in the moments before the failure of the element. Therefore, it appears that using the CFRP EBR strengthening system alters the failure mode of the strengthened elements. The failure, which was previously ductile and ruled by the deformation of the longitudinal strengthening, became almost fragile with the detachment of the CFRP sheet bonded to the concrete substrate.

Figure 8: Load versus displacement of reference beams without strengthening and strengthened (Dalfré *et. al*, 2021)

Figure 9 presents a comparison between the average applied load and average vertical mid-span displacement relationship of the reference beams without strengthening (V1_REF_0_14d and V2_REF_0_14d) and strengthened (V1_REF_CFRP_14d and V2_REF_CFRP_14d), with those kept in the laboratory environment (V1_LAB_CFRP_6m/ V1_LAB_CFRP_27m and V2_LAB_CFRP_6m/ V2_LAB_CFRP_27m) and exposed to weathering (V1_WEA_CFRP_6m/ V1_WEA_CFRP_27m and V2_WEA_CFRP_6m/ V2_WEA_CFRP_27m), respectively.

For the yielding of the steel reinforcement of the strengthened beams maintained in the laboratory environment after 6 (LAB_CFRP_6m) or 27 months (LAB_CFRP_27m), an average increase in load capacity of 4.6 and 6.9 %, respectively, was observed concerning the yielding of the steel in the beams without strengthening (REF_CFRP_14d). Considering the exposure to weathering, an average increase in load capacity of 9.6 and 13.3 %, respectively, was observed after 6 or 27 months for the beams WEA_CFRP_6m and WEA_CFRP_27m when comparing the results with the REF_CFRP_14d.

So, according to the results presented in Table 2 and Figure 9a, a significant decrease in the load-carrying capacity was observed until 6 months. After that, the same load and mid-span displacements were observed along the time.

For the maximum load and considering the elements kept in the laboratory condition, an average increase in load capacity of 40.7 and 44.4 % was obtained after 6 or 27 months when comparing the results of the strengthened (LAB_CFRP_6m or LAB_CFRP_27m) and the reference beams (REF_CFRP_14d). However, for the beams exposed to weathering, lower values were obtained. So, an average increase of 35.2% and 35.9 % were obtained for the beams WEA_CFRP_6m and WEA_CFRP_27m after 6 or 27 months, respectively.

Figure 9: Relationship between Average applied load versus average vertical displacement of beams: Laboratory and (b) weathering

Considering the maximum force recorded in the tests with the strengthened beams (Table 2), the exposure to weather was more aggressive for the strengthening system since its ultimate load was lower than that of the elements maintained in the laboratory environment.

Analyzing the maximum average load of the exposed beams (WEA_CFRP_6m or WEA_CFRP_27m) and considering the results obtained in the tests of the strengthened reference beams (LAB_CFRP_6m or LAB_CFRP_27m), reductions of 13.5 and 19.1%, respectively, were obtained. Also, a reduction of the vertical displacement can be observed when comparing the strengthened elements kept in a laboratory or exposed to weathering.

Concerning the failure load of the strengthened elements exposed to the environments, it was verified that there were no changes when comparing it to the strengthened reference beams, presenting an almost fragile failure, with the detachment of the CFRP sheet bonded to the concrete substrate (Figure 10).

Figure 10: Verified failure mode on the strengthened beams (Dalfré *et. al*, 2021)

CONCLUSIONS

This work reports findings from an experimental program conducted to evaluate the efficiency of the EBR technique in increasing the load capacity of reinforced concrete beams strengthened in flexure with CFRP composites. Also, it evaluates the behavior of EBR-CFRP strengthening systems when exposed to weathering. Two exposure environments were adopted in this study (laboratory and weathering). Beams maintained in laboratory condition for 200 days, with and without strengthening, were considered as the reference (REF), while the remaining beams were exposed to degradation environments and tested at the ages of 380 and 1010 days. The results obtained allowed the following conclusions to be obtained:

- The efficiency of the EBR technique in increasing the load capacity of bending reinforced concrete beams with CFRP sheets was verified by means of significant increases in the load capacity of the strengthened elements. Concerning the steel reinforcement yielding, it was verified that the strengthening provided an increase in the load capacity corresponding to the steel yielding and the

maximum force of 19.7% and 50.4%, respectively. In addition, there was a reduction in the average vertical displacement of 9.7% for strengthened reference beams, compared to those without strengthening, respectively, due to the reduction of cracking that the strengthening system promotes, restricting the reduction of the element's inertia;

- Analyzing the beginning of the steel yielding of the exposed beams and taking into account the results obtained in the tests of the strengthened reference beams (REF_CFRP_14d) showed that the elements exposed to the laboratory environment and those exposed to weathering presented a reduction in the average load at steel yielding of 12.6 and 10.7% and 8.4 and 5.3%, respectively, after 6 and 27 months. It is also possible to observe that the maximum force recorded in the strengthened beams exposed to these environments suffered a reduction of 6.4 and 3.9% and 10.1 and 9.6%, respectively. So, weathering is the most aggressive environment. However, no significant decrease in the load-carrying capacity was verified when comparing the results of the beams kept in the laboratory condition (and the ones exposed to weather);
- Moreover, it was noted that the evolution of the curing time from 7 to 14 days of the primer and saturation epoxy resins maintained in a laboratory environment resulted in statistically equivalent values, i.e., the curing time affected neither the mechanical properties of the specimens nor the behavior of the stress-deformation diagram.
- In the analysis of primer epoxy resin exposed to weathering was observed for the tests performed after 4, 8, 12 and 24 months of exposure reductions up to 62.3 and 31.8% of the tensile stress and modulus of elasticity, respectively;
- From the analysis of the saturation epoxy resin exposed for 4, 8, 12 and 24 months to the weathering, it was found that the tensile strength and the modulus of elasticity reduced up to 63.3 and 16.6%, respectively, from the reference condition with 14 days of cure, and the failure mode changed from ductile to fragile without a plasticization interval; and
- The CFRP composites exposed to the laboratory environment and weathering showed no significant changes in their mechanical properties over the temporal evolution.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest associated with the work presented in this paper.

DATA AVAILABILITY

Data on which this paper is based is available from the authors upon reasonable request.

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